

BUXORO ME'MORCHILIGI: TARIXIY MEROS VA UNING AHAMIYATI**Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyazovich**

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Buxoro qadimdan buyuk sivilizatsiyalar chorrahasida joylashgan, boy tarixiy va madaniy merosga ega bo'lgan shahar hisoblanadi. U Markaziy Osiyoning eng yirik ilmiy, madaniy va savdo markazlaridan biri bo'lib, asrlar davomida musulmon Sharqida ilm-ma'rifat va ma'naviyat markazi sifatida tanilgan. Ayniqsa, Buxoro me'morchilik san'ati Sharq me'morchiligining nodir namunalardan biri sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Bu yerdagi obidalar, madrasalar, masjidlar va minoralar xalqaro miqyosda tan olingan va bugungi kunda ham dunyo ahlining e'tiborini tortmoqda.

Me'morchilik san'ati — bu xalqning tarixiy taraqqiyoti, madaniyati va estetik qarashlarining mujassam ifodasidir. Buxoro me'morchiligi ham qadim zamonlardan to hozirgi kungacha o'zining betakror uslubi, rang-barangligi va shakllari bilan ajralib turadi. Bu maqolada Buxoro me'morchilik maktabining shakllanish bosqichlari, asosiy yodgorliklari va ularning ahamiyati yoritib beriladi.

Buxoro me'morchiligining ilk bosqichlari

Buxoro hududida dastlabki me'morchilik obidalari miloddan avvalgi asrlarga borib taqaladi. Arxeologik qazishmalar natijasida aniqlanishicha, qadimiy Buxoro shahrida mudofaa devorlari, ibodatxonalar va saroylar qurilgan. VII-VIII asrlarda islom dini keng tarqalishi bilan yangi me'moriy shakllar paydo bo'ldi. Jumladan, masjidlar, madrasa va minoralar qurilishi boshlandi.

IX-X asrlarda Somoniylar sulolasi hukmronligi davrida Buxoro shaharsozlik va me'morchilikda katta yutuqlarga erishdi. Bu davrda qurilgan eng muhim inshootlardan biri — Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi bo'lib, u Markaziy Osiyoda to'liq g'ishtdan qurilgan ilk yodgorlik hisoblanadi. A. Asqarov yozadi: "Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi sharq me'morchiligida yangi bosqichni boshlab berdi. Uning nafis g'isht terish uslubi va geometrik naqshlari keyingi davrlarda ham o'rnak bo'ldi" Maqbara to'g'ri to'rtburchak shaklida bo'lib, gumbaz bilan yopilgan. Uning devorlari naqshinkor g'ishtlardan terilgan, har bir g'isht o'z o'rnida bezak sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Bu uslub keyingi yuz yillar davomida Buxoro me'morchiligida asosiy tamoyillardan biriga aylangan.

Karaxoniylar va Saljuqiylar davridagi yodgorliklar

XI-XII asrlarda Karaxoniylar va Saljuqiylar hukmronligi Buxoro me'morchiligiga yangi nafas berdi. Bu davrda monumental inshootlar qurilishi rivojlandi. Minorai Kalon — aynan shu davrda qurilgan va Buxoroning ramziga aylangan. Arslonxon tomonidan 1127-yilda barpo etilgan bu minora 47 metr balandlikka ega va butun shaharni ko'rib turuvchi minoralardan biri hisoblanadi. A. Xolmatov ta'kidlashicha: “Minorai Kalon faqatgina diniy vazifalarni bajarmagan, balki shahar mudofaasi va axborot tarqatish vositasi sifatida ham xizmat qilgan” Bu davrga oid yana bir muhim yodgorlik — Mag'oki Attor masjidi. Bu masjid yer sathidan pastda joylashgani bilan diqqatga sazovor va islomgacha bo'lgan davrlarda ham ibodat maskani bo'lganligi taxmin qilinadi.

Temuriylar va Shayboniylar davrida me'moriy taraqqiyot

XIV-XV asrlarda Temuriylar davrida Buxoro yana yuksak taraqqiyotga erishdi. Bu davrda madrasalar, masjidlar, saroylar qurilishi avj oldi. Ulug'bek madrasasi (1417-1420 yillar) aynan shu davrga to'g'ri keladi. Bu madrasa ilm-ma'rifat maskani bo'lib, o'zining mukammal me'moriy yechimlari bilan ajralib turadi. E. Rtveladze shunday deydi: “Ulug'bek madrasasi nafaqat Buxoroning, balki butun Movarounnahrning yirik ilmiy markazi bo'lgan”.

Shayboniylar davrida (XVI asr) Buxoroda yangi ansambllar qurildi. Mir Arab madrasasi (1535-yil) aynan bu davr yodgorligi bo'lib, zamonaviy Buxoroning eng go'zal binolaridan biridir.

Bu madrasa arab me'moriy an'alarini va mahalliy bezak san'atini mujassamlashtirgan.

Rtveladzening fikricha: “Mir Arab madrasasining naqsh va mozaikalari rang-barang va chuqur ma'noga ega bo'lib, diniy va ma'rifiy ahamiyat kasb etgan”

Ashtarxoniylar va Mang'itlar davridagi qurilish ishlari

XVII-XVIII asrlarda Ashtarxoniylar sulolasi hukmronlik qildi. Bu davrda Labihovuz ansambli qurildi. Ansambлга Nodir Devonbegi madrasasi, xonaqohi va ho'pondan iborat binolar kiradi. Nodir Devonbegi madrasasining asosiy bezaklari hayvon tasvirlari va sirlangan koshinlar bilan boyitilgan bo'lib, bu islom me'morchiligida kam uchraydigan hodisa hisoblanadi.

XVIII-XIX asrlarda Mang'itlar sulolasi hukmronligi davrida Buxoro me'morchiligi yana jonlandi. Abdulazizxon madrasasi (1652-yil) va Chor Minor (XIX asr) bu davr yodgorliklaridan hisoblanadi. Sh. Vohidov bu haqida shunday yozadi: “Abdulazizxon madrasasi naqsh va bezaklarining rang-barangligi va geometrik uyg'unligi bilan ajralib turadi. Unda Eron va Hindiston me'moriy an'alarining ta'siri seziladi” Chor Minor o'zining to'rt minorasi bilan o'ziga xos me'moriy yechimga ega. Har bir minora turli hududlarning madaniyati va uslublarini aks ettiradi.

Buxoro me'morchiligining asosiy xususiyatlari

Buxoro me'morchiligi bir nechta muhim xususiyatlarga ega:

1. G'ishtdan foydalanish. G'isht Buxoro me'moriy inshootlarida asosiy qurilish materiali hisoblanadi. G'ishtlardan turli naqsh va bezaklar ishlangan.

2. Naqsh va bezaklar. Arabeska, geometrik shakllar va koshin bezaklar keng qo'llaniladi.

3. Gumbaz va minoralar. Ko'pchilik masjid va madrasalar markazida katta gumbaz va minoralar barpo etilgan.

4. Fasad va portallar. Inshootlarning asosiy qismi portal bilan bezatilgan bo'lib, ular monumental ko'rinishga ega.

5. Hovli va ichki bog'lar. Madrasalarda va xonaqohlarda keng hovlilar va ichki bog'lar tashkil etilgan.

Xulosa

Buxoro me'morchiligi dunyo me'morchilik san'atida o'ziga xos va betakror o'ringa ega.

Bu me'moriy meros o'zining tarixiy, diniy va estetik ahamiyati bilan ajralib turadi.

Buxorodagi Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi, Mir Arab madrasasi, Minorai Kalon va Labihovuz ansambli kabi obidalar xalqimiz tarixining iftixorli sahifalaridir.

Bugungi kunda bu yodgorliklar O'zbekiston va jahon madaniy merosining ajralmas qismi sifatida muhofaza qilinmoqda. Ularni asrab-avaylash va keyingi avlodlarga yetkazish har birimizning burchimizdir.

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